

H²IOSC
Humanities and cultural Heritage Italian Open Science Cloud

CALL	<p>Ministry of University and Research (MUR), Directorate-General for Internationalization and Communication, Notice D.D. 3264 dated 28/12/2021.</p> <p>Mission 4 "Education and Research" - Component 2 "From research to enterprise" - Investment Line 3.1 "Fund for the realization of an integrated system of research and innovation infrastructure", Action 3.1.1 "Creation of new IRs or strengthening of existing ones that contribute to Horizon Europe's Scientific Excellence objectives and networking"</p>
PROJECT TITLE	Humanities and cultural Heritage Open Science Cloud
PROJECT ACRONYM	H2IOSC
PROJECT ID	IR0000029
PROJECT WEBSITE	https://www.h2iosc.cnr.it
CUP	B63C22000730005
WP	WP6
OU	OU 12 - ISPC-RM
DELIVERABLE NUMBER	6.2
DELIVERABLE TITLE	H2IOSC Services and protocols
EXPECTED DELIVERY DATE	October, 31st 2023
ACTUAL DELIVERY DATE	August, 31st 2024
AUTHORS	Bruno Fanini (CNR ISPC), Francesco Pinna (CNR OVI), Francesco Coradeschi (CNR OVI), Paolo Cignoni (CNR ISTI), Alessandro Muntoni (CNR ISTI), Pietro Sichera (CNR ILIESI), Emiliano Degl'Innocenti (CNR OVI)
<p>This project is funded by the European Union - NextGenerationEU. The views and opinions expressed are only those of the authors and do not necessarily reflect those of the</p>	

European Union or the European Commission. Neither the European Union nor the European Commission can be held responsible for them

Abstract

The activities of WP 6 are devoted to servification, virtualization and remotization of existing tools and services available from the four involved Research Infrastructures (CLARIN, DARIAH, E-RIHS and OPERAS) in H2IOSC. The document first describes objectives and state of the art, then lists refactoring processes carried out, involving servification steps, specifications and protocols adopted to improve access.

ABSTRACT.....	2
LIST OF ACRONYMS.....	4
INTRODUCTION	5
OBJECTIVES	5
STATE OF THE ART.....	8
REFACTORING OVERVIEW	11
REFACTORED SERVICES BY PARTICIPATING RIS	12
CLARIN	13
ILC PI - EPILEXO EDITOR - AN INTERFACE FOR EDITING/CREATING LINKED LANGUAGE RESOURCES FOR ANCIENT LANGUAGES.....	13
ILC PI - ESCRIPTORIUM: A WEB PLATFORM FOR HANDWRITTEN TEXT RECOGNITION (HTR).....	14
DARIAH	15
OVI CNR FI - TLIO, TESORO DELLA LINGUA ITALIANA DELLE ORIGINI	15
OVI CNR FI - PLUTO, PIATTAFORMA LESSICOGRAFICA UNICA DEL TESORO DELLE ORIGINI	16
OVI CNR FI - GATTO, GESTIONE DEGLI ARCHIVI TESTUALI DEL TESORO DELLE ORIGINI	16
OVI CNR FI - TIGRO, TESORO ITALIANO DELLE ORIGINI, GESTORE RICERCHE	17
OVI CNR FI - MIRABILE, ARCHIVIO DIGITALE DELLA CULTURA MEDIEVALE (OWNED BY FEF AND SISMEI).....	18
OVI CNR FI - EVT, EDITION VISUALIZATION TECHNOLOGY	19
OVI CNR FI - RAISE - RESTORE DATA INTEGRATION SUITE	20
OVI CNR FI - TRAME, TEXT AND MANUSCRIPT TRANSMISSION OF THE MIDDLE AGES IN EUROPE (OWNED BY FEF) ..	21
E-RIHS.....	22
ISTI PI - DIGITAL FABRICATION LABORATORY VIRTUAL ACCESS	22
ISPC RM – CAPTURE SERVICE	24
ISPC NA/RM – WEBXR SERVICES FOR HS (ATON)	25
ISPC LE - SENSE: WIRELESS SENSOR NETWORKS FOR CULTURAL HERITAGE CONSERVATION AND MONITORING	27
OPERAS	29
REFERENCES	30

LIST OF ACRONYMS

RI	Research Infrastructure (CLARIN, DARIAH, E-RIHS or OPERAS, in this document)
H2IOSC	Humanities and Heritage Open Science Cloud
CC	Cloud Computing
SOA	Service-Oriented Architecture
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
CLARIN-IT	CLARIN Italian node (Common Language Resources and Technology Infrastructure)
DARIAH-IT	DARIAH Italian node (Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities)
E-RIHS	E-RIHS Italian node (European Heritage Science Research Infrastructure)
OPERAS	OPERAS Italian node (Open scholarly communication in the european research area for social sciences and humanities)
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
REST	Representational State Transfer
SOAP	Simple Object Access Protocol
API	Application Programming Interface
VM	Virtual Machine
OAS	OpenAPI Specification
SSO	Single sign-on

Introduction

The H2IOSC project aims at creating a federated and inclusive cluster of research infrastructures in the ESFRI domain of Social Sciences and Humanities (formerly Social and Cultural Innovation). Specifically, the four involved Research Infrastructures (RIs) are: CLARIN, DARIAH, E-RIHS and OPERAS. The Work Package 6 is devoted to activities related to servification, virtualization and remotization of existing tools and services available from the four involved RIs in H2IOSC.

Objectives

The main goal of activities carried out in the WP6 is to **improve (or enable) access** to rich **tools and services** provided by involved RIs. As already highlighted in D6.1, some of the tools are not yet properly accessible to different communities of researchers, or they are not yet servified.

D6.2 outlines a plan to improve access to the instruments and services offered by the RIs involved in the H2IOSC project. This plan involves: i) the servification of tools, which means making them accessible as services in the H2IOSC cloud, ii) the virtualization of those that cannot be servified, iii) the remotization, enabling remote control of scientific instruments.

The main objective of the activities carried out in WP6 is to improve (or enable) access to the rich tools and services provided by the RIs involved. Following the operational plan for *servification, virtualization, and remotization* introduced in D6.1 and summarized in the following paragraphs, D6.2 describes detailed strategies adopted by the involved RIs and units to strengthen access to services through specific refactoring actions.

Challenges

The variety of tools and services offered by CLARIN, DARIAH, E-RIHS, and OPERAS, described in the specific sections, highlight several challenges. The first challenge we face is related to the different domains, target users and scientific objectives of the existing tools offered by the participating RIs. A second challenge is related to the different level of maturity and readiness as evidenced in the current RI offerings. This translates into different efforts and pace on the part of specific RIs/OUs to align a given service with the common WP6 requirements, or to servify a given tool. Another challenge is on-premise software: applications that are hosted on-premise, as opposed to hosted by a public cloud platform or remote data center. This is quite common for some specialized software tools deployed within labs (or entire RIs). This class often presents significant challenges in terms of servification (e.g.: additional or intensive effort) also due to maintenance, (lack of) access to source code, or poor extensibility.

Servification and Virtualization

Based on the results gathered by WP2, WP6 aim was to classify and parameterize the current internal offering of tools and services available to each RI. This task was inspired by ongoing work related to the IPERION-HS project in E-RIHS to explore methods to improve interoperability among Heritage Science data. Another reference is the current classification in the EOSC portal, that will provide unified access to a European hub of research data, tools,

and services for innovation and education-especially software and services. This initial classification is also particularly useful for mapping the current state of the art concerning servification and providing a first reference to measure the effort required for the refactoring activities. Due to the diversity of tools and services, this effort will be uneven and should be evaluated on a case-by-case basis. Basic information by tool/service included: title, description, category, vendor, RI, keywords, reference links (repositories, active instances, etc.), standards employed, input/output (if applicable). Mapping input/output classes (also one of the key performance indicators in WP6) was particularly important for service composition. For example, such classification should facilitate future automated agents to provide combined solutions for user-given scenarios or to provide recommendations from specific queries or resource types.

Regarding the specific cases of on-premise software tools used among the participating RIs, refactoring may not be a viable solution because of: 1) major efforts required, 2) lack of access to the code, or 3) major reengineering issues. In these cases, virtualization was the preferred choice, working in close coordination with WP4 to make these tools accessible to the reference scientific communities.

Category mapping for each WP6 service was particularly important in determining the scientific areas covered by all RIs when fully implemented and offered to the community at the federation level. Refactoring activities targeting servification are intended to improve (or enable) access to various scientific communities. As highlighted in the internal classification, different levels of maturity, adopted technologies, and target communities emerged.

The first step in WP6 plan was to identify for a given tool the minimum set of functions required with respect to the target community. This involves routines, procedures or features that users need to access. A second step involved investigating access policies by service, including existing authentication protocols, where applicable, to access specific resources.

A further step was also planned towards the consolidation of the H2IOSC federation, through SSO (single-sign on) being investigated in WP4 and also discussed in WP5 (Marketplace). The following steps involve the translation of these selected routines into accessible endpoints per service, following existing REST API guidelines and best practices: independence, evolution, and API design organized around resources. For asynchronous operations (e.g., service routines that may require prolonged processing, thus taking a finite amount of time to complete), common task managers are provided to keep track of computationally intensive operations, while providing appropriate interfaces to keep users informed of progress. The REST refactoring APIs for each service and the strategies adopted will be described in detail in this deliverable.

Remotization

This section describes the remotization protocols being developed to perform remote scientific and technical investigations of artworks using hyperspectral analytical techniques available in E-RIHS' MOLAB platform.

The remote control of experimental operations was designed through a series of closely interconnected components: cyber-physical systems/devices (machines and sensors), middleware (communications and data transfer), cloud (remote data processing and remote VE) and software. The prototype design of the remotization platform consists of: cyberphysical devices (in situ), middleware, remote control, software.

Services Manifests

Given the challenges highlighted, including the variety of domains involved, target communities and technologies, the next step (carried out by Task 6.1), together with all the RIs involved, is the development and definition of a WP6 service manifest. The manifest serves as a “surface descriptor” that enables discovery of the properties and capabilities of a given service, intended for specific integrations such as Marketplace developed in WP5 or local RI catalogs. The manifest structural model is aligned across the four RIs, within the H2IOSC federation, to provide consistent and robust access to service properties and capabilities. The manifest model was developed based on several activities, including: 1. Preliminary activities of WP6 (described in the previous sections) and their intersection with the activities of other WPs (such as WP2, WP3, WP4, and WP5) 2. Existing national/international schemas 3. Ongoing efforts in current (or past) projects.

More specifically, the general schema mainly inherits attributes from the EOSC service model, the E-RIHS service model (v0.7), and the CLARIN switchboard tool schema (v2).

A collaborative document was established among the RIs to refine and evolve the initial draft, including main sections, mandatory and optional attributes, type by attribute, and controlled vocabularies where required (with input from WP4 and WP3).

A corresponding translation into a JSON schema offers some automation advantages in H2IOSC federation: it allows validation of new manifests (i.e., new services wishing to join the H2IOSC federation) and enables automatic generation of input forms for manifest attributes, etc. - for dedicated tools or utilities to generate service manifests.

The service manifest also includes input/output sections of a given service, as well as dedicated technology sections developed in co-design with WP5 (Marketplace) and WP3 (e.g., Readiness Levels). Among the main purposes of the manifest there's the need to provide Marketplace (as well as other H2IOSC actors) with a standardized way to: 1. Present the capabilities of a given service 2. Present descriptive composition (e.g., suggestions on whether and how well two services A and B could be composed and their compatibility level/score) 3. Provide recommendations (e.g., depending on search queries on specific types of resources) for services composability. The manifest attributes also provide details about a given service in terms of its implementation, for comprehensive and enhanced indexing within web portals (local to RIs, but also in the joint H2IOSC Market Place).

State of the Art

REST (representational state transfer) is the architecture used for designing services consumed across different platforms and environments fuelling interoperability (Ehsan et al. 2022, Li et al. 2016).

The two main properties of this architecture are *statelessness* and *cross-platform consumption readiness*: it is nowadays a widely followed and standardized way of publishing services over the Internet. REST emerged as the standard protocol for implementing and consuming these services, which are called RESTful application programming interfaces (APIs). Various surveys did show that various companies have migrated in recent years from XML-supported SOAP (Simple Object Access Protocol) to REST (Kumar et al. 2023), thus making such adoption quite straightforward for newly crafted services.

HTTP verbs in particular plays a fundamental role in determining how clients interact with resources. These standardized HTTP methods, often referred to as HTTP verbs, are at the core of RESTful services, as building blocks of REST API interactions:

GET	used to request data from the server. It is a safe and idempotent operation, meaning it should not have any side effects on the server, and multiple identical GET requests should produce the same result
POST	used to create a new resource on the server. When a client sends a POST request, it typically includes data in the request body that the server uses to create a new resource
PUT	used to update an existing resource on the server. It requires the client to send the entire representation of the resource, even if only a small part of it is being modified
PATCH	used to update an existing resource on the server (like PUT), but it requires the client to send partial data to modify part of the resource
DELETE	is used to remove a resource from the server. When a client sends a DELETE request, it instructs the server to eliminate the specified resource

These verbs can be mapped to specific actions to be performed on resources: *retrieval* (GET); *creation* (POST); *update* (PUT/PATCH); *deletion* (DELETE). There are also two important concepts related to HTTP verbs: *idempotency* and *safety*.

1. *Idempotency*: an operation is idempotent if performing it multiple times has the same effect as performing it once. GET is inherently idempotent, while PUT and DELETE can be idempotent if designed properly. POST, on the other hand, is not idempotent, as creating a new resource each time will have a different effect

2. *Safety*: a safe operation is one that does not modify the state of the server. GET is considered a safe operation, as it does not change anything on the server. However, POST, PUT, and DELETE are not safe, as they can alter server state

The **OpenAPI**¹ Specification (OAS) defines a standard, language-agnostic interface to HTTP APIs which allows humans and computers to discover the capabilities of a service without access to source code, documentation, or through network traffic inspection. When properly defined, a consumer can understand and interact with the remote service with a minimal amount of implementation logic. An OpenAPI definition can be used by documentation generation tools to display the API, code generation tools to generate servers and clients in various programming languages, testing tools, and many other use cases.

Figure 1: sample Pet Store Server based on the OpenAPI 3.0 specification

OAS does not require rewriting existing APIs, nor binding any software to a service – the described service may not even be owned by the creator of its description. However, the service's capabilities need to be described in the structure of the OAS. The OpenAPI

¹ <https://www.openapis.org/>

Specification does not mandate a specific development process such as design-first or code-first. It does facilitate either technique by establishing clear interactions with an HTTP API.

Containerization is a lightweight virtualization technology allowing the deployment and execution of distributed applications on cloud, edge/fog, and Internet-of-Things platforms (Casalicchio & Iannucci, 2020). Each container is a fully functional and portable computing environment surrounding the application and keeping it isolated from other environments (for instance running in parallel on the same server/machine). There are many widely proven advantages offered by containerization:

- easier management of the life cycle of distributed applications
- negligible overhead for when they run either on bare-metal or virtual servers
- (re)start / stop times reduced up to an order of magnitude with respect to virtual machines (VMs)

Docker² is an open platform for developing, shipping, and running applications. It allows to separate *applications* from *infrastructure*, accelerating the delivery process. Docker streamlines the development lifecycle by allowing developers to work in standardized environments using local containers which provide your applications and services (Potdar et al. 2020).

Docker's container-based platform allows for highly portable workloads: a *docker container* is an isolated environment where an application runs without affecting the rest of the system and without the system impacting the application. Since they are isolated, containers are well-suited for securely running software like databases or web applications requiring access to sensitive resources, without giving access to every user on the system. They can run on a developer's local laptop, on physical or virtual machines in data-centers, on cloud providers, or in a mixture of environments.

Docker images are read-only templates containing instructions for creating a container: it creates containers to run on the Docker platform. An image is composed of multiple stacked layers, like layers in a photo editor, each changing something in the environment. Images contain the code or binary, runtimes, dependencies, and other filesystem objects to run an application

² <https://www.docker.com/>

Refactoring overview

This section describes WP6 refactoring processes carried out on each H2IOSC exposed service, based on the D6.1 guidelines, as well as the per-service OAS descriptor, accessible via service manifest as described in D6.1.

OpenAPI descriptors enable discovery of services capabilities from humans, automated harvesters, platforms or other project layers, including H2IOSC MarketPlace (developed in WP5) and its API Manager (developed in WP4).

The following macro-tasks have been identified in WP6 refactoring processes:

1. Identify a set of *functions/routines to be exposed* by the service, starting from the original status
2. Define *authentication* policies (if applicable) for the set and if/how they can be integrated with SSO designed in H2IOSC
3. Translate the set into *REST endpoints*, with proper verbs (see “state of the art” section)
4. Generate accessible *OAS descriptors* (to be linked with service manifest)

To support these activities, 8 different training courses were also arranged by CNR ISPC Rome and Naples OUs, for temporary personnel recruited among the four RIs mainly operating on WP6. More specifically the courses: “Virtualization and Microservices”, “Docker Base”, “REST API”, “Data Visualization”, “Database MySQL”, “Javascript”, “Neural Networks” and “Data Science introduction”.

Regarding REST API refactoring (or equipment) the following guidelines and best practices were adopted:

- *Independence*: any client (internal or external to the H2IOSC federation) should be able to call these functionalities, regardless of how the API is implemented internally
- *Evolution*: The API should be able to evolve and add functionality independently from client applications. Existing client applications should continue to function without modification as the API evolves
- *API design* organized around resources

For asynchronous operations (e.g. service routines that might require a prolonged but finite time to complete), task managers approaches were considered to track computationally intensive operations, while providing proper interfaces or task tracking systems to keep users informed about the progress.

Refactored services by participating RIs

The following table lists all the refactored services by each participating RIs. Each service details the refactoring steps performed, including architectural design (or redesign), access improvements, containerization strategies, as well as challenges encountered during such activities. A unique identifier within the H2IOSC federation will be also assigned to each service.

Service name	RI	OU	Platform
TLIO	DARIAH	OVI-FI	
Pluto	DARIAH	OVI-FI	
GATTO	DARIAH	OVI-FI	
TIGRO	DARIAH	OVI-FI	
Mirabile	DARIAH	OVI-FI	
EVT	DARIAH	OVI-FI	
RAISE	DARIAH	OVI-FI	
TRAME	DARIAH	OVI-FI	
Digital Fabrication Laboratory Virtual Access	E-RIHS	ISTI-PI	yes
Capture Service	E-RIHS	ISPC-RM	
WebXR Services for HS (ATON)	E-RIHS	ISPC-NA/RM	yes
SENSE	E-RIHS	ISPC LE	
AI Services	E-RIHS	ISPC CT	
EpiLexO Editor	CLARIN	ILC-PI	yes
eScriptorium	CLARIN	ILC-PI	yes

CLARIN

The CLARIN-IT services listed here will be displayed via the marketplace and will be documented using methods and protocols such as OpenAPI. The federation authentication service based on an AAI developed by Nanotec will be integrated, while the authorization part and related user role management will be developed at the infrastructure level.

ILC PI - EpiLexO Editor - An interface for editing/creating linked language resources for ancient languages

EpiLexO: an interface for creating lexica for epigraphic languages conformant to Semantic Web principles linked to their testimonies (encoded in TEI-EpiDoc) and related bibliographies.

This service is categorized as Lexicon creation & management; Lexicon lookup & searching. The EpiLexO Editor is the editing GUI interface of the DigitAnt platform; it operates upon a set of independent software back-end components, mainly the LexO-server and the CASH-server. The application is designed to facilitate collaboration among scholars, enabling multiple researchers to work simultaneously on the same datasets in cooperation. The EpiLexO GUI is organised in 3 main sections (or columns), each of them providing a set of different functionalities for different data and information types. The column on the left contains the navigation trees for the main resources: corpus, lexicon, and (lexical) concepts; the column on the right side of the interface displays several panels that contain contextual and additional information such as links to related resources, bibliography, attestations, and metadata. The central column is the main working area devoted to lexicon editing and linking operations, in its 2 horizontal panels, one for Inscriptions, the other for lexical entries. The interface can be considered a functional working prototype, with core functionalities for lexicon processing, creation, and lookup implemented; it is currently in active use by the ItAnt project members. The interface supports basic editing and creation of linked language resources for ancient languages.

Current status

The service is ready to be deployed (upon request).

Refactoring activity

- *completed*
Software analysis

Authentication

Federated authentication is not yet implemented but will be integrated according to the general project standards.

Endpoints

https://digitant.ilc.cnr.it/epilexo_demo/lexicon

OAS

Not available

ILC PI - eScriptorium: a web platform for Handwritten Text Recognition (HTR)

eScriptorium is a web platform which integrates Handwritten Text Recognition (HTR) through kraken HTR engine and cooperative proofreading of automated transcriptions. Through the HTR United Project not only new performant HTR models are provided, but the entire process of image acquisition / recognition / HTR model refinement / proofreading / deposit of digital resources is open and replicable, in compliance to the principle of Open Science.

Current status

The service is not yet active.

Refactoring activity

- N/A

Authentication

Federated authentication is not yet implemented but will be integrated according to the general project standards.

Endpoints

<https://escriptorium.ilc4clarin.ilc.cnr> (not yet installed)

OAS

Not available

DARIAH

The DARIAH services listed here will be displayed via the marketplace and, where appropriate, will also be published on the DARIAH service platform, AEON. The core element underpinning the platform is an API manager, which is currently being implemented, based on WSO2 technology. Within the API manager, the federation authentication service based on an AAI developed by Nanotec will be integrated, while the authorisation part and related user role management will be developed at the infrastructure level.

It will be noted that, compared to the previous deliverable (D6.1), the services

- OVI CNR FI - Raw Data Ingestion Tool Suite
- OVI CNR FI - Semantic Data Ingestion Tool Suite
- OVI CNR FI - Data Management Tool Suite (RAISE-BE)
- OVI CNR FI - Data Visualization Tool Suite (RAISE-FE)
- OVI CNR FI - RAISE Atlante Module
- OVI CNR FI - RAISE Chronos Module

have been integrated into a single service called RAISE (formerly, for abuse of notation, RESTORE).

Finally, a certain affinity between the functionality of GATTO, TIGRO and TLIO may be noted; indeed, it cannot be ruled out that, in a possible future development, some of these functionalities may be merged, but for the time being this has not yet happened, and what follows is a presentation of the current situation.

OVI CNR FI - TLIO, Tesoro della Lingua Italiana delle Origini

This tool falls into the “browsing and querying” category of dictionary studies. It is a web-based search application created by the Institute Opera del Vocabolario Italiano of the CNR. The system is designed to access the TLIO (Treasure of the Italian Language of Origins). It provides an interactive and user-friendly digital interface that allows users to navigate online through the historical lexicon of ancient Italian.

Current status

It still has to be servified, and it will be done later because it has a low priority service, as it does not belong to DARIAH’s pilots. Nonetheless, there are no concerns about any hard issue emerging during the servification activity.

Refactoring activity

- *completed*
Software analysis
- *In progress*
Extraction and re-design of API, refactoring, testing, dockerization, deployment on DC (OVI-FI), publication on API manager, testing.

Authentication

The federation authentication service developed by Nanotec and integrated in the API manager will be used.

Endpoints

Still not available (encompassed by `<http://tlio.ovi.cnr.it/TLIO/ricTLIO2.php>`)

OAS

Still not available

OVI CNR FI - Pluto, Piattaforma Lessicografica Unica del Tesoro delle Origini

This tool is classified as a "browsing and querying" service in the realm of dictionary research. It's a web-based application being crafted by the CNR Opera del Vocabolario Italiano Institute to enable users to tap into the BTV (Bibliografia dei Testi Volgari), which stands as the most comprehensive compilation of bibliographic information on early Italian writings. The project, known as Pluto, seeks to progressively incorporate all TLIO-related resources and instruments into a unified framework, consolidating previously disparate databases and applications into a single, cohesive digital environment.

Current status

This component is yet to be servified. The conversion will be scheduled for a later date due to its low-priority status, as it's not part of DARIAH's main pilot projects. However, there's confidence that the process of turning it into a service won't encounter any significant obstacles or complications.

Refactoring activity

- *completed*

Software analysis

- *In progress*

Extraction and re-design of API, refactoring, testing, dockerization, deployment on DC (OVI-FI), publication on API manager, testing.

Authentication

The federation authentication service developed by Nanotec and integrated in the API manager will be used.

Endpoints

Currently, `http://pluto.ovi.cnr.it/btv/testi_results/`,
`http://pluto.ovi.cnr.it/btv/autori_results/`.

OAS

Still not available

OVI CNR FI - GATTO, Gestione degli Archivi Testuali del Tesoro delle Origini

GATTO is a lexicographic software designed and developed at OVI, created for the construction, management and querying of the corpus of texts on which the Vocabolario

Storico della Lingua Italiana, maintained and managed by OVI, is based. In its servification, GATTO will naturally include the features of GATTOweb (see D6.1), allowing the consultation of the corpus, both lemmatized and not, through a web interface.

Current status

It has yet to undergo the servification process, which will be addressed during the next stage due to its high priority, as it is part of DARIAH's pilot projects. However, there are no significant concerns regarding potential issues arising during the servification process.

Refactoring activity

- *completed*
Software analysis
- *In progress*
Extraction and re-design of API, refactoring, testing, dockerization, deployment on DC (OVI-FI), publication on API manager, testing.

Authentication

The federation authentication service developed by Nanotec and integrated in the API manager will be used.

Endpoints

Still not available

OAS

Still not available

OVI CNR FI - TIGRO, Tesoro Italiano delle Origini, gestore ricerche

Tigro is a lexicographic software designed and developed at OVI, originated as a spin-off and servification of the existing tool GATTO. It allows the construction and querying of corpora of texts, with an initial focus on lexicographic research and texts in ancient Italian, but with a built-in possibility of handling broader linguistic and research contexts. It is in active development. It consists of a web-based GUI along with a set of APIs that allow direct machine-to-machine interaction with both existing and newly defined corpora.

Current status

Beta version, only available on the OVI intranet.

Refactoring activity

- *In progress*
Integration with the authentication service developed by Nanotec, testing to get from beta to full 1.0 version

Authentication

The federation authentication service developed by Nanotec and integrated in the API manager will be used.

Endpoints

No public endpoint is currently publicly available; a test endpoint exists on the OVI intranet. A public endpoint will be made available as soon as the integration with the Auth service is completed.

OAS

An OAS document has already been defined and it has been published at: [OAS on Baltig³](#)
However, it is still not complete as it misses some of the TIGRO's API.

OVI CNR FI - Mirabile, Archivio digitale della cultura medievale (owned by FEF and SISMEL)

MIRABILE is a knowledge management system dedicated to the study and research of medieval culture, encompassing the digital resources provided by SISMEL and FEF. The platform offers online tools that allow users to search through:

- Databases from various research projects in medieval studies, promoted by both institutions and their partners over several decades.
- Electronic versions of journals and collected works published by SISMEL. Edizioni del Galluzzo.

In this context, MIRABILE may serve as a data source, accessible by the services and platforms developed within H2IOSC, specifically by the first DARIAH's pilot, the Digital Philology Hub. Moreover, it may play an important role in the creation of domain-specific vocabularies and thesauri.

Current status

The servification process has not yet been carried out but is scheduled for the next phase, given its medium priority, as it is considered a "nice to have" component of DARIAH's pilot projects. Nonetheless, there are no major concerns about potential issues emerging during the servification.

Refactoring activity

- *completed*
Software analysis
- *In progress*
Extraction and re-design of API, refactoring, testing, dockerization, deployment on DC (OVI-FI), publication on API manager, testing.

³ CNR authentication required

Authentication

The federation authentication service developed by Nanotec and integrated in the API manager will be used.

Endpoints

Still not available

OAS

Still not available

OVI CNR FI - EVT, Edition Visualization Technology

As part of the RESTORE project, DARIAH-IT, based at OVI, developed a customized version of the EVT (Edition Visualization Technology) application, which is intended to be further developed and employed for the creation of the H2IOSC Scientific Pilots. The original EVT is an open-source, lightweight tool designed to facilitate the creation of digital editions from TEI XML-encoded texts, removing the need for scholars to engage in web programming. It provides end users with a user-friendly interface to browse, explore, and study digital editions. DARIAH-IT's version of EVT was designed to offer advanced navigation features, allowing users to thoroughly explore the lexicographic details of a text. The DARIAH-IT team, as part of the RESTORE project, added support for the management and display of lexicographic data. OVI resources were used as a case study and can now be viewed in EVT with all their lexicographic components (such as lemmas, hyperlinks, and additional information). This enables the examination of different instances of a lemma within the same text, its normalized form, grammatical category, and more. Additionally, the newly introduced mode allows users to view both text and images, making it easier to consult digital facsimiles alongside text transcriptions within the same interface.

Current status

The service is currently on hold as we are assessing whether it is truly necessary for DARIAH's pilot projects. The external provider responsible for developing the Digital Philology Hub has already implemented an effective visualization tool using TEI publisher technology, which fully covers all the required features of EVT.

Refactoring activity

- *completed*
Software analysis
- *In progress*
As its status remains on hold, we will not proceed with any further implementation

Authentication

The federation authentication service developed by Nanotec and integrated in the API manager will be used, unless we will keep the service status on hold.

Endpoints

Not available

OAS

Not available

OVI CNR FI - RAISE - Restore dAta Integration Suite

RAISE, a spin-off of the RESTORE project, is a collection of tools for data ingestion, semantization, storage and visualization. Its main components are:

- A set of command-line tools to assist data managers in the tasks such as data ingestion, filtering, cleaning, semantization.
- A triple store (an instance of Openlink Virtuoso) enriched with custom APIs for data storage and querying
- A modular, customizable web-based GUI for data visualization.

Current status

The servification of the toolset is partial; some of the services are offline-only (source code is available, users are responsible for their use and implementation, with limited support available from the Dariah team).

Refactoring activity

- *In progress*
Servification of additional services, development of the web interfaces to improve interoperability and reusability, adding support for different DB solutions, Integration with the authentication service developed by Nanotec.

Authentication

The federation authentication service developed by Nanotec and integrated in the API manager will be used.

Endpoints

No public endpoint is currently available. Test endpoints exist on the OVI intranet for those services that already have APIs. Public endpoints for API-enabled services will be made available as soon as the integration with the Nanotec Auth service is completed.

OAS

OAS documents are already defined for those services that are API-enabled, but they are not publicly available; they will be made available as soon as the APIs are opened to the internet.

OVI CNR FI - TRAME, Text and manuscript transmission of the Middle Ages in Europe (owned by FEF)

The TRAME initiative, backed by the Italian Ministry of Education and led by the Ezio Franceschini Foundation, seeks to enhance the evolution and interoperability of web-based resources focusing on medieval manuscript heritage. At its core, TRAME aims to foster synergy among digital archives housing scanned images of Middle Age texts, alongside their physical characteristics, literary significance, and cultural impact within the broader context of Europe's historical narrative. This collaborative effort brings together various repositories to create a more comprehensive and accessible resource for scholars and enthusiasts of medieval literature and history.

Current status

The transformation of this element into a functional service is still pending. Given that it's not included in DARIAH's primary experimental initiatives, this task has been assigned a lower priority and will be addressed at a future point. Despite the delay, there's no anticipation of any major challenges or roadblocks arising during the service conversion process.

Refactoring activity

- *completed*
Software analysis
- *In progress*
Extraction and re-design of API, refactoring, testing, dockerization, deployment on DC (OVI-FI), publication on API manager, testing.

Authentication

The federation authentication service developed by Nanotec and integrated in the API manager will be used.

Endpoints

`<http://trame.fefonlus.it/trame/index.php>`

OAS

Still not available.

E-RIHS

ISTI PI - Digital Fabrication Laboratory Virtual Access

We plan to establish a software infrastructure for allowing virtual access to ISTI-PI Digital Fabrication Laboratory within the framework of the H2IOSC project's WP6. The primary objective is to facilitate researchers in obtaining physical replicas from their digital models. This will be achieved by expanding the existing server-based mesh processing infrastructure, originally designed for creating multiresolution representations of 3D models, to incorporate fabrication-oriented processing operations.

- The Digital Fabrication Laboratory at ISTI-PI will house a range of high-end and consumer-grade digital fabrication equipment. As part of its service offering within the E-RIHS network, ISTI-PI will implement a platform for users to upload 3D models for printing.
- The platform will process the uploaded models, preparing them for fabrication tasks. Users will have access to tools for identifying and rectifying potential problems in their models, thereby streamlining the fabrication workflow and enhancing its predictability.
- This platform will leverage ISTI-CNR's existing open-source mesh processing framework, MeshLab, and its server-side Python counterpart for on-demand processing.
- The existing software infrastructure for processing user-uploaded meshes, initially intended for creating streamable multiresolution representations of complex 3D assets, will be augmented to include fabrication-specific mesh processing functionalities

Deployment:

We are refactoring existing base code to allow simpler deployment on cluster-based server architecture like the one provided by H2IOSC, using containerization framework like docker. We are planning to generate an OAS descriptor for the refactored service to enhance its discoverability within the H2IOSC framework. We are evaluating various possibilities about the actual hosting of the platform.

ISPC CT - AI/ML solution for multimodal datasets

Network trained and tested for usage with X-ray fluorescence (XRF) instrumentation of ISPC CT. It has been successfully used for the analysis of a number of cultural heritage objects. At this point this includes paintings both modern and historic, Egyptian amulets and herculaneum papyri. The outlook is to further develop the analysis to other analytical techniques followed by extensions to multimodal datasets. We have built an AI solution for combined analysis of XRF and X-ray diffraction (XRD) which is now being tested. In the future we plan to construct a solution for combined analysis of XRF and RIS imaging.

The network architecture and trained networks are planned to be publically available in the future.

AI/ML approaches provide many advantages during data analysis and processing. It allows users to analyse XRF data on-the-fly during measurement providing a high-fidelity output in the real time while significantly reducing expertise needed. This is particularly useful in on-the-site measurements as it provides guidance helping to improve quality and relevance of the results. Further, such analysis is also closely connected to the remotization task introduced in WP 6.7.

Another scenario is advanced analysis of large multimodal datasets remotely. With growing size and complexity of data obtained by the modern hyperspectral instruments the increased the demand on computational power, time and expertise required for the analysis.

Servification of the AI solutions is designed to help users to perform analysis remotely without access to the computational resources.

At the current state the tool takes as an input XRF datacube and generates elementalcomposition maps. The foreseen inputs are multimodal datacubes.

Deployment:

The tool is currently not implemented as a service, but the creation of the service is underway, where a functional prototype has been developed. The service will be deployed at ISPC CT datacenter.

ISPC CT - Multimodal datasets visualization tool

Toolsuite for real-time interactive analysis of XRF datasets. It implements both classical deconvolution approaches as well AI/ML for the data analysis described above. While the software is still under development it is already being used during measurements that are part of the MOLAB platform of E-RIHS. Tool for analysis of XRD datasets. The tool aims to provide capability for automatic and semiautomatic phase identification using XRD and hyperspectral data. The analysis of the XRD dataset is done using classical Algorithms. Recently we have developed a prototype AI for the combined analysis of XRD and XRF data. The development of tools for analysis of other hyperspectral analytical techniques are planned in the future. Currently we are extending our model to combine analysis XRF and RIS data.

At the moment there is a lack of software for advanced interactive interrogation of multimodal datasets. This tool aims to allow the user to interact with data obtained using different analytical techniques provided within the MOLAB platform of E-RIHS at once in a concise manner.

The inputs are experimental datasets. The general outputs are graphs and images. In practice this encompasses various scientific results of interest such as elemental composition maps and/or maps indicating materials present.

Deployment:

The tool is currently not implemented as a service but is used as an on-premises software. The service implementation is currently underway. It will be deployed at ISPC CT datacenter.

ISPC RM – Capture service

The E-RIHS Capture service offers a set of functionalities to track and record interactive sessions performed in remote infrastructural nodes, public exhibits or online web-applications - targeting analytics.

Service requirements led to the design of scalable architecture able to handle and track incoming anonymized interaction states via network connection - and storing them on a dedicated capture hub, or multiple capture hubs (Fanini & Gosti 2024). The capture service can be part of a wider pipeline involving a suite of web-based services dedicated to analytics workflows, allowing examination/filtering of incoming raw data, and then process such data using for instance Machine Learning models (e.g. pilot 7.7).

The service was developed ex-novo within the H2IOSC project, following guidelines from D6.1 and designing a flexible set of routines to be exposed and accessed by scientific communities willing to track generic interactive sessions.

A flexible architecture was designed in terms of session tracking and retrieval, custom state definition (e.g., custom attributes to track), reliability considerations and an on-demand model. The final protocol between the client application and the capture hub where the service is deployed, is here described:

1. The client application requests a new session, including the intended attributes to track (e.g. 2D/3D coordinates, time, etc.)
2. If the capture service responds successfully, a new session is initiated on the hub and the unique ID is sent to the client
3. The client application is now able to send progressive data chunks to the hub, with custom policies

For the first step, the client application formalizes a list of attributes that will be tracked during the session. This may include spatial attributes (like virtual/physical 3D locations, eye movements, focal points, HMD location in physical space, GPS coordinates, etc.), interaction states related to the application logic or equipment (like BCI headsets' EEG voltages for each channel, wearable device signals, etc.) or other attributes.

Session ID allows access to current record (CSV or other formats) via REST API, to retrieve tracked data.

OAS:

<https://raw.githubusercontent.com/phoenixbf/capturehub/main/services/openapi.json>

Git repository:

<https://github.com/phoenixbf/capturehub>

Deployment:

The service will be deployed on a dedicated and public hub inside the “Area della Ricerca di Roma 1” (CNR) using a cluster model, and it will be part of the H2IOSC pilot 7.7.

A docker image is also provided

Authentication:

The service is based on Node.js and an integration with federated authentication service (SSO) developed by CNR Nanotec is foreseen.

ISPC NA/RM – WebXR Services for HS (ATON)

ATON⁴ is an open-source framework (Fanini et al. 2021) developed by CNR ISPC based on large open-source ecosystems (such as THREE.js and Node.js) and modern web standards to create interactive, liquid and collaborative Web3D/WebXR apps targeting Heritage Science. Its adaptive presentation layer allows interactive 3D visualization on all devices, ranging from mobile (smartphones, tablets) up to PC/workstations and immersive XR devices, without any installation required for final users. It offers a modular architecture and event-driven API to craft rich, immersive or collaborative Web3D tools or experiences. It is based on interoperable web standards allowing maximum reuse and integration with other services, especially within the H2IOSC complex ecosystem.

Within H2IOSC, the service will be used by different E-RIHS WP7 pilots, specifically: “Illuminated Manuscripts” (ISPC LE), “HeriVerse” (ISPC LE), “Immersive Analytics Hub” (ISPC RM) and “Prototyping platform for Virtual / Physical Exhibitions” (ISPC FI).

Refactoring:

Under task 6.3, refactoring activities focused on:

- A complete re-design of existing REST API
- Re-design of the plug&play web-apps architecture
- Implementation of plugins (“flares”) architecture
- Re-design of core micro-services for improved flexibility (e.g. custom authentication models, etc...)

Following guidelines and best practices established in WP6 and its interactions with other WPs, the new REST API (v2) was re-designed around specific resources:

- Collection items (3D models, panoramic content, media, etc.)
- 3D scenes (arrangements of collection items)
- Users
- Apps
- Flares (plugins)

For each of the above, a persistent identifier is provided for retrieval or manipulation via REST API. Refactoring actions were also carried out to facilitate the integration of the service with ongoing development of a few E-RIHS pilots requiring it. Previous REST API (v1) will be still operational for a time to guarantee backwards compatibility.

H2IOSC project and the variety of the E-RIHS pilots requiring this service, indeed led to focus several activities on further improving extensibility. The plug&play architecture of the service was redesigned to accelerate integration of *vertical* web-applications (e.g. E-RIHS pilots with specific focus or domain), allowing single instances to host one or more Web3D/WebXR

⁴ <https://aton.ispc.cnr.it/site/>

applications. This allows also flexibility in terms of physical deployment (e.g. single instance with several apps, or more instances handling separate apps) depending on datacenters availability and request volumes foreseen.

“Flares” (plugins) were designed and implemented under task 6.3 for *horizontal* extension: similarly to apps architecture, flares can be plugged dynamically on a given instance, to enrich both client and server functionalities. A single web-app (e.g. a pilot) can thus require one or more plugins, depending on project requirements. To assess such functionalities, a flare is being developed targeting survey domain (survey-flare). The flare system will be also used to provide integration with the federated authentication service (SSO) developed by CNR Nanotec, or other authentication models.

Figure 2: vertical (apps) and horizontal (flares) extensibility of the refactored service

OAS:

<https://raw.githubusercontent.com/phoenixbf/aton/master/services/API/openapi.json>

Git repository:

<https://github.com/phoenixbf/aton>

Deployment:

The service will be deployed in Naples and Lecce Datacenters, using cluster mode. Depending on specific pilots’ requirements, minor instances could be deployed in other nodes of the H2IOSC federation. A docker image is also provided.

Authentication:

The service is based on Node.js and an integration with federated authentication service (SSO) developed by CNR Nanotec is foreseen. This will also allow a few E-RIHS pilots using this service to directly exploit SSO for custom logic.

ISPC LE - SENSE: Wireless sensor networks for cultural heritage conservation and monitoring

The Wireless sensor network will gather and transmit measured data on cultural heritage, making them available for remote analysis, post-processing and visualization at the DIGILAB level. From the hardware point of view, microcontroller unit-based modules will be in direct contact with the distributed sensors and actuators at different sites on one side and datacenters on the other side through wired and wireless communication protocols and standards.

The Message Queuing Telemetry Transport (MQTT) protocol, offering lightweight and efficient communication mechanisms, has been selected for connecting WSN nodes and facilitating data exchange.

The data acquired by the WSN management middleware platform are sent to an open-source software DIGILAB component that allows the analysis, post-processing and presentation of heterogeneous geolocated data in the domain of cultural heritage. The component will request the data from the WSN using its API and present them through interactive and customizable multi-tenant dashboards.

The designed large-scale WSNs can enable remote monitoring and smart control of cultural heritage sites, reducing the need for physical interventions and enhancing the overall efficiency of preservation efforts. Moreover, the platform will allow the creation of connections between the collected data in several research contexts of the cultural heritage field, promoting their sharing and accessibility.

Due to the heterogeneity of monitored sites and technologies used, the design of a WSN will be based on abstract models of its components. In particular, the creation of the networks will consist of a first step in which it will be possible to create the WSN as a composition of abstract elements, and a second step in which the abstract elements will be instantiated through their configuration.

A first phase of study involved the research for devices and sensors available on the market that can be applied in the field of cultural heritage monitoring. These devices and sensors detect environmental and structural parameters, capable of providing information on the state of tangible assets and their evolution in time. Characteristics taken into consideration were low energy consumption, low cost, and the communication way.

Subsequently, use cases that best represented the large case of situations in which these devices could be applied were studied.

Based on this information, the requirements of the software platform (SENSE) were defined. In particular, the following modules will be implemented:

- **SENSE WSN Modeler:** allows to model the WSN by means of a visual interface. The WSN will be represented in the form of a graph, i.e. a set of nodes (abstract node) connected each other. Each node and its link have specific properties, e.g. gateway,

sensor, etc. Users can model their own WSN starting from a model (WSN template) or from scratch as a composition of abstract nodes. The choice of the WSN template is guided by the characteristics of the site/object to be monitored and the purposes of the monitoring itself. The output of the SENNSE WSN Modeler editor is the abstract WSN model;

- The SENNSE WSN Configurator is a full-web application that allows the configuration of the abstract elements (abstract node) of the abstract WSN model defined in the SENNSE-WSN Modeler. The configuration of the abstract model allows to obtain the WSN concrete model;
- The SENNSE User Manager allows to define and manage the different types of local users and to interface with external “authentication and identification” systems;
- The Rule System: is the module that defines the rules through which specific actions are activated when a particular event occurs (based on the data received from the sensors), such as, for example, sending notifications via e-mail;

OAS:

Under development

Deployment:

The service will be deployed in Lecce Datacenter. The hardware part is under development at SciFablab and DhiLab in Lecce, while as regard the software part, a mandate was given to an external software company.

Authentication:

The service authentication will be integrated with federated authentication service (SSO) developed by CNR Nanotec is foreseen. Moreover, the user profile to access specific service features will be stored inside DIGILAB platform (see WP 3.1). DIGILAB platform will provide explicit API to allow the access to user profile

OPERAS

OPERAS does not have refactoring activities because it did not have services already developed. Research and cataloguing environments, such as Leibniz's Correspondents and Acquaintances, will be transferred to the new infrastructure.

References

- Ehsan, A., Abuhaliqa, M. A. M., Catal, C., & Mishra, D. (2022). RESTful API testing methodologies: Rationale, challenges, and solution directions. *Applied Sciences*, 12(9), 4369
- Li, L.; Chou, W.; Zhou, W.; Luo, M. Design Patterns and Extensibility of REST API for Networking Applications. *IEEE Trans. Netw. Serv. Manag.* 2016, 13, 154–167
- Neumann, A.; Laranjeiro, N.; Bernardino, J. An Analysis of Public RESTWeb Service APIs. *IEEE Trans. Serv. Comput.* 2018, 14, 957–970
- Kumar, K., Jain, A. K., Tiwari, R. G., Jain, N., Gautam, V., & Trivedi, N. K. (2023, April). Analysis of api architecture: A detailed report. In 2023 IEEE 12th International Conference on Communication Systems and Network Technologies (CSNT) (pp. 880-884). IEEE.
- Ruan, B., Huang, H., Wu, S., & Jin, H. (2016). A performance study of containers in cloud environment. In *Advances in Services Computing: 10th Asia-Pacific Services Computing Conference, APSCC 2016, Zhangjiajie, China, November 16-18, 2016, Proceedings 10* (pp. 343-356). Springer International Publishing.
- Ferreira, A. P., & Sinnott, R. (2019, December). A performance evaluation of containers running on managed kubernetes services. In 2019 IEEE International Conference on Cloud Computing Technology and Science (CloudCom) (pp. 199-208). IEEE.
- Casalicchio, E., & Iannucci, S. (2020). The state-of-the-art in container technologies: Application, orchestration and security. *Concurrency and Computation: Practice and Experience*, 32(17), e5668.
- Potdar, A. M., Narayan, D. G., Kengond, S., & Mulla, M. M. (2020). Performance evaluation of docker container and virtual machine. *Procedia Computer Science*, 171, 1419-1428.
- Kane, S. P., & Matthias, K. (2023). *Docker: Up & Running*. O'Reilly Media, Inc.
- Fanini, B., & Gosti, G. (2024). A New Generation of Collaborative Immersive Analytics on the Web: Open-Source Services to Capture, Process and Inspect Users' Sessions in 3D Environments. *Future Internet*, 16(5), 147. <https://doi.org/10.3390/fi16050147>
- B. Fanini, D. Ferdani, E. Demetrescu, S. Berto, E. d'Annibale (2021). ATON: An Open-Source Framework for Creating Immersive, Collaborative and Liquid Web-Apps for Cultural Heritage. *Applied Sciences*, 11(22), 11062.